

Data-Driven Strategies in Human Resource Management: The Role of Information Science in Workforce Resilience – A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

In a time characterized by swift technological advancements and increased workforce vulnerabilities, incorporating data-driven strategies into Human Resource Management (HRM) has become essential for bolstering organizational resilience. This systematic review investigates how information science influences HRM practices through data-driven strategies designed to address workforce resilience. Workforce resilience is a central concept in organizational sustainability in the context of accelerating change, digital disruption, and global crises. The review used PRISMA, a thorough search of the Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar databases identified 47 peer-reviewed studies published from 2012 to 2024 that met the inclusion standards. These studies were examined to assess the use of data driven strategies in HRM such as predictive analytics, AI-driven workforce analytics, and real-time monitoring systems in HRM. The review revealed five central themes, the strategic imperative of data-driven HRM, enhancing workforce resilience through predictive analytics, information systems supporting workforce decision-making, the role of artificial intelligence in HRM, and challenges and considerations in implementing data-driven HRM. The analysis highlights that data-driven HRM is both a technological enhancement and a strategic necessity. In addition, organizations that integrate data analytics into HR processes are better positioned to anticipate workforce disruptions, optimize talent acquisition, and support employee well-being.

KEYWORDS: Human Resource Management, Human Resources, Data-Driven Strategies, Information Science, Workforce Resilience, Predictive Analytics, Artificial Intelligence

1 INTRODUCTION

In the age of digital transformation, organizations worldwide are increasingly relying on data to shape decision-making processes across all departments (Okon, et al., 2024). Human resource management (HRM), which was once driven predominantly by intuition and administrative practices, has entered a new era characterized by technological integration and data-driven strategies (Minbaeva, 2018). This shift is propelled by the increasing availability of workforce-related data and the emergence of digital tools, including predictive analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning and the emerging of the fourth industrial revolution (Conte & Siano, 2023). Data driven strategies and information science tools are transforming how human resources (HR) professionals attract, manage, and retain talent, enhancing organizational agility and long-term sustainability (Bersin, et al., 2016; & Okon, et al., 2024). In recent years, one of the primary objectives of modern HRM has evolved to focus on

building and sustaining workforce resilience, which entails an organization's ability to anticipate, respond to, and recover from workforce-related disruptions (Setiawan, et al., 2025). A resilient workforce ensures continuity during crises but also fosters innovation and adaptability in the face of change. Data-driven HRM strategies play a vital role in strengthening this resilience, allowing employers to make proactive decisions and tailor employee experiences based on real-time insights (Zhang, 2024). At the heart of this integration of data-driven strategies and HRM lies information science. Nguyen and Martin (2022) highlight that information science in organisations is a discipline that is dedicated to the effective collection, classification, storage, retrieval, and dissemination of information. Hence, the incorporation of information science principles into HRM practices enables organisations to derive meaningful insights from employee data, thus transitioning HRM from a reactive function to a proactive strategic partner (Setiawan, et al., 2025). Information

sciences have enacted systems that enables organizations to monitor workforce trends, predict employee behaviour, and implement targeted interventions with precision (Oliver & Kim, 2022).

Research has recognized the increasing influence of data driven analytics and AI in various HR functions, such as recruitment, performance management, employee well-being, and succession planning (Meyer & Allen, 2022; Okon, et al., 2024; & Mishra, 2021). Predictive data analytics allows HR professionals to anticipate employee turnover and pinpoint high-potential candidates early, AI-driven chatbots enhance HR service delivery and boost employee engagement (Bersin, 2019). These advancements are technological improvements which signify a major shift in how HR professionals utilize data, make informed decisions, and contribute to organizational objectives (Yamin, 2024). Despite these advancements, the adoption and usage of data-driven HRM strategies varies significantly across industries and regions due to challenges like data governance issues, ethical dilemmas, and insufficient technical expertise among HR staff (Leicht-Deobald et al., 2019). Furthermore, despite most organizations have implemented some form of HR analytics, few have systematically integrated it into essential HRM practices or explicitly linked it to workforce resilience. This gap highlights the necessity for further research on how data-driven tools and information science frameworks are being used to tackle critical workforce risks and improve organizational adaptability.

This paper provides a systematic review of the academic literature published from 2012 to 2024, focusing on the relationship between data-driven HRM strategies, workforce resilience, and information science. Guided by the PRISMA methodology, the review evaluates empirical and conceptual studies that investigate the application of digital tools, predictive models, and AI technologies in HRM contexts. The objective is to compile existing knowledge on how data is utilized in HRM to predict and tackle workforce-related challenges while emphasizing the contribution of information science in supporting this endeavour. The identification of patterns, insights, and research gaps, adds to the expanding knowledge base at the intersection of HRM, technology, and workforce resilience.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptualizing Workforce Resilience

According to Lim & Hur (2024), workforce resilience is a central concept in organizational sustainability in the context of accelerating change, digital disruption, and global crises. According to Wood & Phillip (2022), workforce resilience refers to the capacity of employees to collectively adapt, recover, and thrive amid adversity, stress, and continuous transformation. The traditional notions of resilience emphasize bouncing back from setbacks, however, modern

definitions extend to proactive adaptability, psychological strength, and the ability to maintain performance under pressure (Lim & Hur, 2024). In the context of HRM, workforce resilience is about enduring change and leveraging it as a springboard for growth and innovation (Soomro et al., 2022). Workforce’s resilience has several key dimensions which include adaptability, emotional intelligence, and social cohesion (DeGraves, 2023). Adaptability enables employees to adjust to new roles, technologies, or work conditions (Kuman & Kumar, 2024). Emotional resilience is the psychological ability to remain positive and focused during periods of stress or uncertainty (DeGraves, 2023). Social cohesion entails strong interpersonal relationships and trust among colleagues to foster collective support systems that enhance organizational endurance (Bento & Garotti, 2019; & Kumar & Kumar, 2024). In addition, Lim & Hur (2024) state that continuous learning is a critical component of workforce resilience which ensures that employees remain equipped with the skills needed to meet evolving demands. These dimensions work together to form a dynamic capability that is increasingly recognized as a strategic asset.

workforce resilience is important in modern organizations because of complex problems and challenges such as talent shortages, economic instability, dynamic and volatile business environment, and health pandemics (Bardoel, et al., 2014; & Meyer & Allen, 2022). Having a resilient workforce has become key in sustaining business continuity and driving transformation. According to Kuntz et al. (2017), organizations that invest in cultivating workforce resilience are better positioned to respond to change, maintain productivity, and retain top talent. The 2008 economic depression and the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the necessity of resilient workforces, as employees were forced to rapidly shift to remote work, balance family responsibilities, and adopt unfamiliar digital tools (Nguyen and Martin, 2022). Organizations which had existing workforce resilience-building strategies, such as strong communication systems, learning platforms, and wellness programs, were able to navigate the COVID-19 crisis more effectively than their counterparts. In addition, Robertson et al., (2015) posit that resilience is deeply intertwined with agility and performance. Organizational agility refers to the ability to sense and respond to environmental changes quickly and effectively. A resilient workforce serves as the foundation for this agility, allowing organizations to reconfigure resources, redesign workflows, and make rapid decisions without descending into chaos (Shin et al., 2012). Moreover, resilient teams are often characterized by higher levels of engagement, innovation, and discretionary effort which are factors that contribute directly to organizational performance outcomes. Research by Hartmann et al. (2020) indicates that workforce resilience buffers against shocks and enhances strategic responsiveness as well as competitive advantage.

2.2 The Evolution of HRM in the Digital Era

HRM has undergone a significant transformation over the past few decades, shifting from a traditionally administrative function to a strategic enabler of organizational performance (Sani, et al., 2024). In the past, Stone, et al., (2015) indicate that HRM used to focus on personnel administration, compliance, and record-keeping, using paper-based or basic digital tools with limited analytical capacity. Traditional HRM approaches were reactive with minimal integration into core business strategies. However, with the rise of digital technologies, HRM has evolved into a data-driven, proactive function that plays a pivotal role in enhancing workforce agility, organizational resilience, and long-term competitiveness (Okon, et al., 2024; & Bhardwaj, et al., 2025). The transition from traditional to digital HRM practices is driven by the need for speed, flexibility, and responsiveness in managing human capital (Mazurchenko & Maršíková, 2019). In contrast to manual HR practices, digital HRM leverages automation, cloud computing, artificial intelligence (AI), and data analytics to streamline recruitment, onboarding, performance management, and employee engagement (Marler & Parry, 2016). These technologies improve operational efficiency and support evidence-based decision-making, shifting HRM from intuition-led to insight-led management (Conte & Siano, 2023). The evolution of HRM into the digital mode has been fuelled by several key variables such as globalisation, technological advancement, impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the availability of workforce data. The globalization of talent has increased competition for skilled labour, requiring more agile and scalable human resources practices, and the rise of remote and hybrid work models accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has made digital tools essential for communication, performance tracking, and collaboration (Bhardwaj, et al., 2025; & Koveshnikov et al., 2022). In addition, the explosion of workforce data ranging from social media activity to internal performance metrics has opened new frontiers for HR analytics, enabling organizations to proactively manage employee well-being, diversity, and productivity (Tursunbayeva, et al., 2018). Technology is playing a pivotal role in enabling strategic HRM as it is allowing organizations to align workforce planning with broader business goals by providing real-time insights into talent capabilities, risks, and development needs. Strategic HRM is no longer confined to policy development but now involves using dashboards, predictive models, and decision-support systems to drive long-term talent strategies (Bondarouk & Brewster, 2016). Moreover, digital platforms such as Human Capital Management (HCM) systems and Learning Management Systems (LMS) support a continuous learning culture, leadership development, and employee engagement which is vital for building a resilient and future-ready workforce (Dahlbom, et al., 2020).

2.3 Data-Driven Strategies in HRM

According to Conte & Siano (2023), the emergence of data-driven strategies in HRM has revolutionized how organizations manage, evaluate, and optimize the workforce. Data-driven strategies depend on human resources analytics, predictive tools, and artificial intelligence (AI) to derive actionable insights from employee data, enabling more informed decision-making and strategic alignment (Tuli, et al., 2018). As businesses face increasingly complex challenges such as talent shortages, employee disengagement, and workforce instability, Jensen-Eriksen (2016) states that the integration of advanced analytics into HRM is proving indispensable for improving resilience and organizational outcomes. HR analytics, often referred to as people analytics or workforce analytics, involves the systematic identification and quantification of the people drivers of business outcomes (Levenson, 2018). Workforce analytics includes metrics such as employee turnover rates, time-to-hire, performance ratings, engagement scores, and diversity ratios (Marler & Boudreau, 2017). Rasmussen and Ulrich (2015) state that HR metrics are used to assess current workforce status and to forecast future trends and recommend interventions. Predictive analytics represents a more advanced application of HR data that leverages machine learning models and statistical techniques to forecast outcomes such as employee attrition, promotion likelihood, and job performance (Brown, 2019). Predictive HR analytics helps organizations move from reactive to proactive HRM. Predictive models can highlight employees at risk of leaving based on factors like tenure, workload, recent performance changes, or disengagement patterns (Bersin, 2018). In recruitment, predictive tools assess candidate suitability by analyzing application data and comparing it with profiles of successful past hires (Van den Broek, Bos-Nehles, & Frie, 2021). This speeds up hiring and improves the quality of new talent and reduces hiring bias. In addition, John and Hajam (2024) acknowledge that workforce analytics benefits include accurate skill gap identification, and staffing need predictions.

In addition, data-driven HRM allows real-time monitoring using AI applications. Real-time analytics platforms collect and analyse data on employee behaviour, productivity, well-being, and collaboration patterns as they happen (Qama, et al., 2021). Tools like Microsoft Viva or workplace analytics software provide insights into communication flows, meeting loads, and focus time, helping HR practitioners to address issues like burnout or collaboration silos (Minbaeva, 2020). Furthermore, AI-powered chatbots are now used to respond to employee queries, guide onboarding processes, and collect feedback continuously thereby creating a more responsive and personalized employee experience. Jain (2018) states that AI enhance learning and development strategies through adaptive learning systems that recommend personalized

training modules based on employee roles, performance data, and career goals. These smart systems ensure that employees are constantly reskilling and upskilling, which is vital for workforce resilience in fast-changing industries (Sivathanu & Pillai, 2018). Moreover, sentiment analysis algorithms can detect early signs of dissatisfaction or disengagement by analysing employee communication data, offering HR teams an early warning system to intervene before problems escalate.

2.4 The Role of Information Science in HRM

According to Al Shobaki (2017), information science is a discipline that provides foundational principles and tools that support the effective management of data across various domains including HRM. The core functions of information science are data collection, organization, storage, retrieval, analysis, and visualization which are increasingly indispensable in navigating the complexities of modern workforce management (Obeidat, 2012). As organizations transition toward digital and data-driven HR strategies, Information Science offers both theoretical frameworks and practical technologies that enable smarter, faster, and more informed HR decisions (Debayo et al., 2024). Information Science is concerned with the lifecycle of information, from creation and acquisition to processing and dissemination. This lifecycle aligns closely with HR functions that depend on continuous data collection, data processing, and communication of insights to stakeholders (Roul, et al., 2024). The application of information science principles enables HR professionals to comprehend the workforce behaviours, identify trends, and make proactive decisions that improve organizational resilience and adaptability (Obeidat, 2012). Cloud-based Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) such as SAP SuccessFactors, Workday, and Oracle HCM enable the structured collection of large volumes of employee data ranging from demographic information to performance metrics and development goals (Mazen, et al., 2017). HRISs are often integrated with external data sources, including labour market analytics and employee sentiment platforms, broadening the informational base for workforce planning. Through proper data management techniques guided by information science principles, HR departments ensure data integrity, privacy, and accessibility, all of which are vital for compliance and effective decision-making (Al Shobaki, 2017).

In addition, information systems play a critical role in the analysis and visualization of HR data. Tools such as Tableau, Power BI, and Qlik Sense allow HR practitioners to transform raw data into visual dashboards that reveal patterns, correlations, and anomalies (Bondarouk, et al., 2017). These visualizations help non-technical stakeholders quickly grasp complex workforce trends, such as absenteeism spikes or diversity imbalances, and take corrective action. In addition, data modelling techniques drawn from library and information science research enable a more sophisticated understanding of employee behaviour, such as identifying predictors of turnover or career stagnation (Kudyba, 2020). Other than analytics, Bondarouk, et al., (2017) elucidate that information systems grounded in information science support decision-making by enabling real-time, evidence-based responses to workforce challenges. Decision support systems (DSS) and expert systems can simulate various HR scenarios, such as the impact of reducing headcount or launching a training initiative, allowing management to make data-informed choices. These systems often incorporate machine learning algorithms that evolve with new data, enhancing their predictive capabilities over time (Margherita, 2021). The integration of information science into HRM strengthens the organization's ability to harness the full potential of workforce data.

3 METHODS

This study employed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines to conduct a systematic review of literature examining the integration of data-driven strategies in Human Resource Management (HRM) through the lens of Information Science. The objective was to explore how organizations leverage data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), and digital tools to enhance workforce resilience. A comprehensive and systematic search was conducted out across three major academic databases, which are Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, covering literature published between 2012 and 2024. The search strategy combined keywords and Boolean operators, including: "data-driven HRM strategies," "workforce resilience," "information science," "predictive analytics in HR," and "AI in human resources".

Figure 1 PRISMA flow diagram

Figure 1 illustrates the article selection and review process.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The systematic review aimed to synthesize existing literature on the integration of data-driven strategies in HRM with a focus on enhancing workforce resilience through the application of information science. The literature selection process followed the PRISMA guidelines, ensuring transparency and replicability in study selection and inclusion. As indicated in Figure 1 above, an initial database search was conducted across Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, yielding 312 records published between 2012 and 2024. 30 duplicate records were removed, a total of 282 unique articles were subjected to title and abstract screening. During this stage, 210 records were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria, primarily due to limited focus on data-driven HRM, lack of relevance to workforce

resilience, and insufficient technological and information science linkage. In addition, the remaining 72 full-text articles were retrieved and assessed for eligibility based on predefined inclusion criteria:

- Empirical or conceptual studies focusing on data-driven tools or technologies in HRM;
- Relevance to workforce resilience
- Peer-reviewed and published in English between 2012 and 2024.

Following the full-text assessment, 25 studies were excluded. The reason for exclusion was based on not focusing on data-driven HRM (n =10), not addressing workforce resilience (n =8), and date out of range (n =7). This process resulted in the inclusion of 47 studies in the final qualitative synthesis. The synthesis of the existing literature on data-driven strategies in

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HRM aimed at enhancing workforce resilience through information science, several qualitative themes have emerged. These themes encapsulate the core areas where data-driven approaches intersect with HRM to bolster workforce resilience.

4.1 The Strategic Imperative of Data-Driven HRM

Ahmić & Ćosić (2024) highlight that the advent of HR analytics has enabled organizations to systematically analyse

employee data, leading to more informed decision-making processes. This technological and strategic shift aligns HR functions more closely with overarching business objectives and enhances organizational agility. The synthesis of several studies confirms that data-driven HRM is imperative. Table 1 below provides a summary of studies whose findings shows the importance of data-driven HRM.

Table 1: Studies Related to the Strategic Imperative of Data-Driven HRM

Author(s)	Year	Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Georgescu et al.	2024	Strategic HRM and organizational culture	Quantitative	Data-driven HRM enhances strategic alignment and resilience through cultural integration.
Ahmić & Ćosić	2024	Digital HRM and resilience	Quantitative	Strategic use of digital HR tools leads to improved anticipation and adaptive capacity.
Gardezi et al.	2024	HR analytics in supply chains	Quantitative	HR data analytics provide strategic input into workforce planning and supply chain resilience.
Panda et al.	2024	AI as a driver of HR resiliency	Review	AI-based systems enable strategic HR interventions for future workforce planning.
Majam & Jarbandhan	2022	Big data in public HRM	Theoretical	Big data helps public sector HR to shift from reactive to strategic, enhancing service delivery.
Akter et al.	2024	Post-COVID digital maturity in HRM	Thematic Analysis	Strategic transformation through digital maturity enhances resilience in turbulent environments.
Nosratabadi et al.	2022	AI and employee lifecycle	Review	Strategic workforce lifecycle management is strengthened by AI and predictive analytics.
Qin et al.	2023	Talent analytics using AI	Survey	Data-driven talent analytics support strategic retention and succession planning.

This theme emphasizes how integrating data driven strategies into HRM enables evidence-based decision-making, predictive workforce planning, and alignment of human capital strategies with long-term organizational goals. As indicated in Table 1 above, the studies consistently highlight that data-driven HRM is no longer optional but strategic approach in organisations. Studies reviewed emphasises that organizations that strategically embed data driven HRM are more likely to anticipate workforce challenges, respond swiftly to external disruptions, and align talent strategy with corporate goals. For example, Georgescu et al. (2024) show how strategic HRM, supported by data, mediates the influence of organizational culture on resilience. Similarly,

Akter et al. (2024) emphasize digital maturity as a key strategic enabler post-COVID.

4.2 Enhancing Workforce Resilience through Predictive Analytics

This theme focuses on how predictive analytics leveraging historical and real-time HR data through advanced algorithms enables organizations to anticipate workforce challenges, mitigate risks, and enhance overall resilience. Predictive analytics in HR involves using machine learning, statistical models, and AI to forecast employee turnover, performance dips, skills shortages, and potential burnout, allowing pre-emptive interventions that maintain workforce stability and adaptability (Akter et al; 2024; & Gardezi et al., 2024).

Table 2: Studies on Enhancing Workforce Resilience through Predictive Analytics

Author(s)	Year	Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Qin et al.	2023	AI techniques for talent analytics	Quantitative	AI-based predictive models improve retention by forecasting employee turnover and engagement.
Nosratabadi et al.	2022	AI in employee lifecycle management	Review	Predictive analytics enables proactive lifecycle management, enhancing workforce resilience.
Panda et al.	2024	AI-driven HR resiliency	Mixed Methods	Machine learning models predict workforce risks, allowing timely HR interventions.

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Akter et al.	2024	Digital maturity and HR resilience	Thematic Analysis	Digital tools, including predictive analytics, are critical for adaptive workforce strategies.
Majam & Jarbandhan	2022	Big data in HRM for public sector resilience	Quantitative	Predictive analytics supports forecasting HR needs in public service, reducing workforce disruptions.
Gardezi et al.	2024	Supply chain resilience through HR analytics	Quantitative	Predictive analytics enhances workforce planning and crisis readiness in supply chains.
Ahmić & Ćosić	2024	Digital HRM and organizational resilience	Quantitative	Predictive tools contribute to anticipating workforce challenges and sustaining resilience.

As indicated in Table 2, the integration of predictive analytics in HRM allows HR professionals gain foresight into workforce trends and vulnerabilities, which supports proactive workforce planning, risk management, and strategic talent development (Gardezi et al., 2024). Workforce resilience refers to the capacity of employees and the organization to adapt, recover, and thrive amid challenges and changes. Predictive analytics plays a crucial role in fostering this resilience by providing foresight into potential workforce issues and enabling pre-emptive interventions (Akter et al., 2024; & Ahmić & Ćosić, 2024). Data analysis on employee performance, engagement levels, and external factors, organizations can predict which employees are at risk of burnout or disengagement (Majam & Jarbandhan, 2022). The results allow the HRM practitioners to implement targeted wellness programs, adjust workloads, or provide additional support to at-risk employees, thereby preventing productivity losses and promoting a healthier work environment (Nosratabadi et al., 2022). Moreover, predictive analytics facilitates succession planning by identifying employees with the potential to fill critical roles in the future. This ensure Predictive analytics is central to workforce resilience by equipping HR with the ability to foresee potential disruptions before they materialize. Qin et al. (2023) demonstrate that AI-

driven talent analytics can reduce attrition through early identification of at-risk employees. In the same vein, Nosratabadi et al. (2022) highlight how predictive models help in lifecycle management, preparing organizations for workforce changes proactively. Furthermore, integrating predictive analytics into digital HRM systems as discussed by Akter et al. (2024) allows for continuous monitoring and rapid adaptation, which is critical in volatile business environments. The harnessing of data insights, allows organizations to mitigate risk but also foster an agile, resilient workforce capable of sustaining performance under pressures and remain resilient in the face of leadership transitions or unexpected departures, maintaining stability and continuity.

4.3 Information Systems Supporting Workforce Decision-Making

This theme explores the critical role of information systems in facilitating effective, timely, and evidence-based workforce decision-making. As organizations confront dynamic challenges ranging from talent shortages to economic volatility integrated HR information systems, decision support systems, and enterprise analytics platforms are increasingly being leveraged to guide strategic and operational workforce choices (Trivellas et al., 2023).

Table 3 Studies on Information Systems Supporting Workforce Decision-Making

Author(s)	Year	Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Trivellas et al.	2023	HRIS capabilities and strategic decision-making	Quantitative	Strong HRIS infrastructure significantly improves decision quality and organizational agility.
Farndale & Paauwe	2022	Strategic HRM and information technology	Conceptual	Integration of HRM and IT enhances responsiveness and global talent decision-making.
Akter et al.	2024	Digital maturity and HR transformation	Thematic analysis	Information systems support predictive and real-time decision-making in resilient HRM.
Majam & Jarbandhan	2022	Big data and IS in public HRM	Theoretical	IS tools like HRIS and DSS enable data governance and smarter HR policy formation.
Afiouni et al.	2022	HR technology and organizational performance	Case study	HRIS adoption facilitates evidence-based decisions and improves HR efficiency and trust.
Papalexandris et al.	2023	HRIS and employee engagement	Mixed methods	HRIS enables consistent engagement tracking and supports proactive HR planning.
Gardezi et al.	2025	IS in supply chain workforce resilience	Quantitative	Integrated IS improve HR coordination and forecasting in high-risk sectors.

Majam & Jarbandhan (2022) highlight that information systems allow HR professionals to access real-time insights,

automate complex analyses, simulate scenarios, and align decisions with broader organizational goals. This enables data

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transparency and decision traceability, information systems contribute directly to organizational agility and workforce resilience (Trivellas et al., 2023). The implementation of sound information systems is fundamental to the effective application of data-driven strategies in HRM (Papalexandris et al., 2023). HRIS serve as centralized repositories for employee data, enabling efficient data management and retrieval. HRIS systems support various HR functions, including payroll, benefits administration, performance evaluations, and compliance reporting (Afiouni et al., 2022). In addition, advanced HRIS platforms integrate analytics capabilities, allowing HR professionals to provide insights into workforce demographics, turnover rates, and recruitment metrics, facilitating data-driven planning and policy development (Papalexandris et al., 2023). Furthermore, integrating HRIS with other enterprise systems ensures a holistic view of organizational performance, aligning HR strategies with business outcomes (Farndale & Paauwe, 2022). Information systems play a foundational role in modern workforce decision-making, enabling HR to transition from administrative tasks to strategic functions. Trivellas et al. (2023) demonstrate that the analytical capabilities of HRIS platforms improve decision precision

and responsiveness. In addition, Akter et al. (2024) highlight the use of digital dashboards for real-time workforce insights, crucial during crises or rapid organizational shifts. Decision support systems (DSS) also emerged as critical tools for modelling potential workforce scenarios, helping managers evaluate options and outcomes before implementation. In the public sector, Majam & Jarbandhan (2022) show how information system contributes to policy innovation and data accountability. As organizations seek agility and resilience, IS integration across departments ensures that HR decisions are aligned with broader operational and strategic goals, creating a data-enabled culture of continuous improvement (Gardezi et al., 2024).

4.4 The Role of Artificial Intelligence in HRM

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming HRM by automating processes, enhancing decision-making, and providing predictive insights. This theme explores how AI technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing (NLP), and robotic process automation (RPA) are integrated into HR functions to improve efficiency, accuracy, and strategic workforce management.

Table 4: Studies on the Role of AI in HRM

Author(s)	Year	Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Tursunbayeva et al.	2023	AI in public sector HRM	Systematic Review	AI improves decision-making and administrative efficiency but raises ethical and transparency concerns.
Margherita & Bua	2021	AI for HR planning in Industry 4.0	Conceptual	AI enhances strategic workforce planning and automates repetitive HR tasks.
Panda et al.	2024	AI and HR resiliency	Mixed Methods	AI predicts workforce risks and optimizes employee support initiatives.
Qin et al.	2023	Talent analytics and AI	Quantitative	AI-based predictive models identify talent gaps and improve retention strategies.
Nosratabadi et al.	2022	AI in employee lifecycle management	Review	AI supports the entire employee lifecycle, from onboarding to offboarding, enhancing resilience.
Strohmeier & Piazza	2015	Algorithmic decision-making in HRM	Theoretical	AI systems can outperform human judgment in structured HR decisions but require careful oversight.
Upadhyay & Khandelwal	2018	Ethical implications of AI in HRM	Literature Review	Highlights the need for transparency and fairness in AI-driven HR processes.

The integration of Artificial Intelligence in HRM marks a significant shift from traditional, reactive personnel management to proactive and strategic workforce management. Studies such as that of Qin et al. (2023) and Nosratabadi et al. (2022) illustrate how AI enables organizations to forecast attrition, personalize learning experiences, and automate performance feedback, thereby enhancing workforce resilience and productivity. AI's role spans the entire employee lifecycle from talent acquisition and onboarding to performance management, learning, development, and retention (Nosratabadi et al., 2022). AI supports workforce resilience by providing tools for proactive

risk mitigation, personalized engagement, and data-driven policymaking (Strohmeier & Piazza, 2015). In addition, AI has revolutionized HRM by automating routine tasks, providing deeper insights through data analysis, and enhancing decision-making processes. AI-powered tools can analyze vast amounts of data to identify trends and patterns that may not be immediately apparent to human analysts (Qin et al., 2023). This capability is particularly beneficial in areas such as talent acquisition, where AI algorithms can sift through large candidate pools to identify individuals who best match the organization's needs. In the context of workforce resilience, AI can monitor employee sentiment through

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natural language processing and sentiment analysis tools. By evaluating communication patterns, feedback, and other indicators, AI can alert HR to emerging issues within teams or departments, allowing for timely interventions. Additionally, AI-driven learning platforms can personalize training content for employees, facilitating continuous skill development and adaptability. In addition, Tursunbayeva et al. (2023) warn, however, that AI's application in HRM in the public sector should be balanced with ethical considerations such as transparency and accountability. Strohmeier & Piazza (2015) emphasize the risks of over-reliance on algorithmic decisions without human oversight. Despite AI's contribution to efficiency, personalization, and agility, the literature suggests the importance of governance frameworks to ensure

fairness and mitigation of bias (Upadhyay & Khandelwal, 2018).

4.5 Challenges and Considerations in Implementing Data-Driven HRM

Despite data-driven strategies offers significant benefits in HRM, their implementation is often fraught with challenges. This theme explores organizational, technical, ethical, and cultural barriers that organizations face in adopting data-driven HRM systems. In addition, this theme also highlights the strategic considerations necessary for successful implementation, such as change management, data literacy, and alignment with organizational values. Table 5 provide studies on challenges in implementing data-driven HRM.

Table 5. Studies on Challenges in Implementing Data-Driven HRM

Author(s)	Year	Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Angrave et al.	2016	Why HR can't become data-driven	Qualitative	HR lacks analytical capability and strategic orientation to fully leverage analytics.
Marler & Boudreau	2017	HR analytics adoption	Conceptual review	Adoption is hindered by a lack of skills, data quality, and leadership engagement.
Bassi	2011	The persistent barriers to HR analytics	Conceptual	Resistance to evidence-based practice and data skepticism are major obstacles.
Rasmussen & Ulrich	2015	Barriers to HR analytics implementation	Case study	Trust, ethics, and decision-making autonomy issues challenge analytics adoption.
McCartney et al.	2021	Skill gaps in the data-driven HR workforce	Quantitative	Many HR teams lack the quantitative skills needed to interpret and apply data insights.
Isson & Harriott	2016	People analytics and predictive HR challenges	Theoretical	Predictive models are hard to implement due to noisy HR data and weak institutional support.
Redman & Wilkinson	2020	Ethics in algorithmic HR practices	Literature review	Ethical dilemmas in data collection, employee monitoring, and bias in algorithmic systems.

Data-driven HRM offers the promise of evidence-based decisions, workforce optimization, and predictive resilience, however, the road to effective implementation is rarely smooth. Angrave et al. (2016) argue that a strategic mindset and data fluency are often absent in HR departments, limiting their capacity to adopt analytics tools meaningfully. Marler & Boudreau (2017) identify data fragmentation and lack of executive buy-in as critical barriers, McCartney et al. (2021) point out widespread skill gaps in HR teams that inhibit proper use of data insights. In the same vein, Isson & Harriott (2016) warn that predictive models struggle to gain traction due to inconsistent data governance and poor system integration. A significant concern raised by Redman & Wilkinson (2020) and Rasmussen & Ulrich (2015) involves ethical and trust issues employees may resist analytics-based practices if they perceive them as intrusive or biased.

5 CONCLUSION AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

This systematic review synthesized literature from 47 studies published between 2012 and 2024 to explore how data-driven

strategies, grounded in information science, are transforming HRM with a focus on enhancing workforce resilience. The review revealed five central themes, the strategic imperative of data-driven HRM, enhancing workforce resilience through predictive analytics, information systems supporting workforce decision-making, the role of artificial intelligence in HRM, and challenges and considerations in implementing data-driven HRM. The analysis highlights that data-driven HRM is both a technological enhancement and a strategic need. In addition, organizations that integrate data analytics into HR processes are better positioned to anticipate workforce disruptions, optimize talent acquisition, and support employee well-being. This proactive approach is critical in a volatile global landscape marked by pandemics, economic uncertainty, and rapid technological shifts. Predictive analytics emerged as a core enabler of workforce resilience. leveraging machine learning models and longitudinal data enables HR teams to forecast attrition risks, performance trends, and skills gaps allowing for targeted interventions. Such foresight enhances individual employee outcomes and organizational agility. The integration of

information systems such as HRIS, learning management systems, and workforce planning dashboards enables evidence-based decision-making across all HR functions. These systems facilitate real-time data visibility, reduce administrative burden, and support data-driven leadership. In addition, AI is also playing a growing role in transforming HRM in areas such as talent sourcing, sentiment analysis, and personalized employee learning. However, the use of AI raises ethical questions about bias, transparency, and accountability. Despite these risks, AI, when designed and governed responsibly, holds significant potential to enhance HR efficiency and employee satisfaction.

The practical implications of adopting data-driven strategies in HRM are profound in building a resilient workforce capable of adapting to rapid change. Organizations should prioritize the development of data literacy within HR teams, ensuring staff can interpret and act on insights derived from advanced analytics and AI tools. This upskilling should be complemented by investments in sound and interoperable information systems that support seamless data integration across departments. To mitigate ethical and legal risks, companies should establish transparent data governance frameworks that protect employee privacy and promote responsible use of algorithms in recruitment and performance evaluations. Cross-functional collaboration between HR, IT, and executive leadership is essential to align technological capabilities with strategic objectives, ensuring analytics tools are technically sound and contextually relevant. Moreover, fostering a data-driven culture where evidence-based decision-making is the norm and innovation is encouraged will enhance the overall effectiveness of HRM.

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